

ISSUES OF COOPERATION BETWEEN THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE AND THE MEDIA

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Abstract: This article analyzes the issues of cooperation between the prosecutor's office and the media. Most importantly, attention is paid to the general goals, tasks, directions, forms, and tactics of interaction between prosecutors and the media, as well as issues of increasing its effectiveness. In addition, the prosecutor's office focuses on the specific aspects of the media in overseeing the implementation of laws and combating crime.

Keywords: prosecutor's office, mass media, legality, human rights and freedoms, violations of the law, openness, protection, cooperation.

The prosecutor's office of the Republic of Uzbekistan fulfills the tasks facing the state in its activities, and the success of carrying out these functions directly depends on the role of the mass media. This is due to the fact that the mass media have an invaluable influence on conveying the policy being implemented in state activities to the public. Especially in the 21st century, in the era of technological advancement, that is, in a digitized society, these broad opportunities have opened up. Consequently, the mass media act as the main bridge in the formation of relations between various subjects (citizens and organizations). At the same time, the mass media perform multifunctional functions in society. Among these relations, an important place is occupied by issues related to defining the general goals, objectives, directions, forms, and tactics of interaction between prosecutors and the media, as well as existing organizational and legal conditions for increasing its effectiveness. Prosecutor's offices can successfully organize interaction with the mass media by strengthening their capabilities and the capabilities of the mass media in achieving their goals in the implementation of prosecutorial supervision and other activities established by law.

This is primarily stated in Article 5 of the Law "On the Prosecutor's Office," according to which the prosecutor's office carries out its activities transparently by regularly informing the public about its activities in overseeing the implementation of laws and combating crime, ensuring access to information about its activities by individuals and legal entities in the manner prescribed by law.¹

Issues of interaction between the media and the prosecutor's office are considered as one of the most important areas of ensuring legality and prosecutorial oversight in the activities of the prosecutor's office. The following main areas of interaction between the prosecutor's office and the media can be distinguished: informing the population about the state of legality and law and order; providing information on prosecutorial investigations and prosecutorial

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси 2001 йил 29 августдаги 257-П-сонли “Прокуратура тўғрисида”ги Қонуни.

measures taken in connection with the detection of serious violations of legislation; verifying the legality of criminal cases initiated on crimes that have attracted public attention, reporting the results of their preliminary investigation and judicial proceedings, as well as refuting inaccurate information and promoting legislation. In addition, it is required to organize the work of the prosecutor's office with the public in such a way that every positive result of the prosecutor's activity is covered in the mass media at the maximum level and in a timely manner, daily monitoring of the work of subordinate employees to bring materials to publicity is required, and each employee is required to regularly appear in the mass media. Such efforts ultimately increase citizens' trust in the state (justice), fight crime, and most importantly, strive for people to live in peace and tranquility.

The main tasks of the prosecutor's interaction with the mass media are: daily monitoring of the activities of the mass media and main Internet sites on the ground in order to promptly inform about violations of legislation, emergencies and other important events; updating online news related to the activities of the prosecutor's office; verification of email messages received by the "Online Reception" section of the official website of the prosecutor's office at the request of citizens, etc. Solving the tasks facing the prosecutor's office, establishing the procedure and nature of interaction (dialogue) of the prosecutor's office in the mass media, allowing a correct understanding of the importance of state power and public consciousness, is an important element in this direction.

An important element in this area of activity is the establishment of a procedure and nature of interaction (communication) that will help the prosecutor's offices solve their problems and clearly understand by the public the role and significance of the prosecutor's office in the system of state power. Prosecutors often publish in print media at both the regional and city (district) levels. Work with the media in the prosecutor's office, like other activities of the prosecutor's office, is based on planning. A corresponding annual (or semi-annual) plan is drawn up, which indicates the publication deadlines and specific executors. The prosecutor's office constantly monitors the execution. This will ensure regular coverage of the activities of the district (inter-district) prosecutor's office. The prepared articles will be published in district newspapers and can also be posted on the websites of district khokimiyats. In order to establish cooperation with district newspapers, meetings with responsible employees and newspaper editors are held every six months. Usually, mutual understanding is achieved, the necessary space is allocated for the publication of materials of the inter-district prosecutor's office. In addition, separate special issues of district newspapers at the end of the year are entirely devoted to the activities of the prosecutor's office or the activities of the prosecutor's office and other law enforcement agencies in the district. In general, this work is not particularly difficult.

Information disseminated through print or electronic media has a long-term impact. Prosecutors ensure the preliminary examination of materials before their submission. This review is not final, because after media workers have finalized and edited the material and selected the title to avoid distorting information and creating incorrect text, it will be reviewed by prosecutors and prepared for publication after approval.

This is because Article 33 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that restrictions on the right to seek, receive, and disseminate information are permitted only to the extent necessary to prevent the disclosure of state secrets or other legally protected

secrets in accordance with the law.² Consequently, the prosecutor's office should take measures to prevent the disclosure of information related to state secrets in its activities and materials related to criminal cases.

According to Article 353 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the investigator, inquiry officer, prosecutor, and court have the right to declare all information in a criminal case or information contained in a specific part thereof undisclosed.³ On this basis, he may obtain from persons participating in investigative actions or present at the performance of investigative actions, or familiarizing themselves with the investigation materials, a written undertaking not to disclose information contained in the case without his permission. The receipt also contains a warning about liability under Article 239 of the Criminal Code for violating this obligation (disclosure of inquiry or preliminary investigation data without the permission of the investigator, inquiry officer, or prosecutor).⁴ Article 162 of the Criminal Code establishes liability for the disclosure or transfer of state secrets, that is, for the disclosure of information constituting state, military, or official secrets by a person to whom this information was entrusted or who was aware of it in connection with his official or professional activity.⁵

Thus, information that cannot be disclosed includes matters related to their activities and official secrets. State secrets include information that constitutes a state secret and (or) official secret, the disclosure of which may harm the security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and is included in the list of information subject to state protection and confidentiality. Official secrets are information relating to any sphere of activity of organizations using state secrets, including military, economic, political, scientific-technical, production, intelligence, counterintelligence, operational-search activities, the disclosure of which may harm the interests of these organizations. Official secret may be an integral part of a secret of state importance.⁶ Therefore, the dissemination of this type of information should be carried out in coordination with the leadership of higher prosecutor's offices. Working with electronic media, such as radio and television, as well as news agencies, also has its own peculiarities. In conclusion, it should be noted that for the prosecutor's office to achieve positive results in working with the media, it is necessary to combine the two-component method: systematic and constant preparation of publications on the activities of the prosecutor's office for placement in district newspapers and on the websites of district khokimiyats; establishing contacts with the mass media in the event of important news; as well as covering the results of the activities of the prosecutor's office with information agencies, including on television and radio, and solving the tasks facing the prosecutor's office, allowing for a correct understanding in the mass media of the role of the prosecutor's office, state power, and public consciousness.

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